

ANTECEDENTS OF THE SUCCESS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF LOCAL ADMINISTRATIVE ORGANIZATIONS IN SARABURI PROVINCE

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Abstract

Creating success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province represents the enhancement of people's quality of life, which arises from good governance as well as participation of all stakeholders who cooperate in the development of security in various dimensions, develop capacities at all levels, and reduce inequality towards the development within the framework of the sustainable development goals. However, with the rapid social and economic changes, there are more and more problems occurring to people. Therefore, local government organizations need to develop their capacity for effective public service management. The objectives of this research were to: 1) study levels of public participation, good governance principles, leadership, human resources in the organization, policies and operational strategies, management innovation and success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province; 2) examine influences of public participation, good governance principles, leadership, human resources in the organization, policies and operational strategies, and management innovation on the success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province; and 3) develop a model for the success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province. This research employed a mixed research methodology combining quantitative and qualitative methods. For the quantitative research part, the research sample consisted of 400 residents in Saraburi Province. The sample size was determined based on the criterion of 20 times the observed variables. They were selected via multi-stage sampling. Data were collected with the use of a questionnaire and analyzed with a structural equation model. As for the qualitative research component, in-depth interviews were conducted with 20 key informants consisting of executives of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province. The findings showed that: 1) public participation, good governance principles, leadership, human resources in the organization, policies and operational strategies, management innovation, and success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province were rated at a high level; 2) public participation, good governance principles, leadership, human resources in the organization, policies and operational strategies, and management innovation had an influence on the success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province, with a 0.5 level of statistical significance; and 3) the model for the success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province, developed by the researcher, was called the 2PILGHS Model, consisting of P (referring to public participation), I (referring to management innovation), L (referring to leadership), P (referring to policies and operational strategies), G (referring to good governance), H (referring to human resources in the organization), and S (referring to success of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province). The 2PILGHS Model is a model for managing local government organizations through the use of concepts and creative, modern and timely methods aiming to serve people in the area and improve their quality of life. These findings can be applied as a guideline for formulating policies that create sustainable success in the management of local administrative organizations.

Keywords: Antecedents/ Success in the Management of Local Administrative Organizations/ Saraburi Province

1. Introduction

Local administrative organizations have vital importance in any society due to the effective role in various operations (Vongsiriwan, 2022). Creating success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province represents the enhancement of people's quality of life. It can be achieved through good governance as well as participation of all stakeholders who cooperate in the development of security in various dimensions, develop capacities at all levels, and reduce inequality towards the development within the framework of the sustainable development goals. However, with the rapid social and economic changes, there are more and more problems occurring to people. Therefore, local government organizations need to develop their capacity for effective public service management.

Local administrative organizations in Thailand are facing several issues which have negative effect on their performance. To promote good governance of these organizations the performance and different operations must achieve the satisfactory level. The sustainability in the success of various operations is mandatory to achieve good governance (Adendorff & Halkias, 2014). However, there are number of issues facing by the local administrative organizations in Thailand to get success in different activities of these organizations in local area. Although these organizations achieved reasonable success in most of the operations (Chatchawan, Trichandhara, & Rinthaisong, 2017; Vongsiriwan, 2022), however, still the improvements are required in different areas.

Most importantly, these organizations are facing several issues in Saraburi province of Thailand. This province of Thailand required improvements in different sectors as well as industries at the satisfactory level of welfare. More specifically, these organizations are facing the issue of various policies as well as operational strategies. Although the government organizations are developed different strategies and policies for different activities in local areas but the implementation of these activities are not achieved and the sustainability is one of the major issues. Furthermore, these organizations are also facing the problem of leadership which has major influence on the failure of various activities. The top management leadership (Babalola et al., 2022; Greenbaum, Babalola, Quade, Guo, & Kim, 2021) has not achieved the reasonable level to guide all the employees for the successful activity. Additionally, it is also found that the public participation in various activities is not addressed by the management of these organizations. The absence of public participation lead towards the failure of various plans and the implementation of regulations. Furthermore, it is also observed that the innovation is key element among the organizations (Ciric, Lalic, Gracanin, Palcic, & Zivlak, 2018), however, among the local administrative organizations of Thailand, the management of innovation is below the satisfactory level. This is one of the major problems among these organizations because in the competitive environment and the era of industrialization the role of innovation is key. Therefore, all these issues have negative effect on the level of success in various operations of these organizations which are needed to address.

This study addressed several issues related to the local administrative organization which were not addressed by the previous studies. Number of studies on government organizations or local administrative organizations in various area have not considered these issues. The problem of management of innovation, lack of leadership and lack of public participation is not addressed by the literature. All these issues are addressed in various other organizations, however, in the context of local administrative organizations is not addressed. In this way, the current study addressed all these issues in relation to the success of these organizations in various activities. Therefore, the specific objectives of the current study or as follows; 1) to study levels of public participation, good governance principles, leadership, human resources in the organization, policies and operational strategies, management innovation and success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province; 2) to examine the influences of public participation, good governance principles, leadership, human resources in the organization, policies and operational strategies, and management innovation on the success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province; and 3) to develop a model for the success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Concepts and Principles for the Success of the Local Administrative Organization

Local administrative organizations aimed to promote welfare among the societies (Chatchawan et al., 2017; Praditsil, Saensano, & Archeewa, 2022; Vongsiriwan, 2022) with the help of the implications of various principles, rules and regulations. Number of local administrative organizations are working in several local areas in Thailand which has the responsibility to promote welfare among the society by keeping the law and order. There are several important elements of local administrative organizations in Thailand. The important elements considered to evaluate the good governance of these organizations. Rule of law has significant importance which is one of the important elements of these organizations and it can be used to evaluate these organizations along with their performance. The rules, regulations, ordinance and notifications in line with the society and their implementation is most important. Furthermore, morality and ethics is another important element of these organizations. Generally, it is based on to promote the capacity building, sincerity as well as discipline in the society which lead towards the peace as well as welfare. Additionally, other important element which belongs to the local administrative organizations is transparency (Butprom et al., 2021). The transparency in various activities related to the government in different areas is most important which has significant influence on the level of trust among the general public. To gain the confidence of the general public these organizations must have significant level of transparency among several activities. The government agencies should consult with public to gain information from the people and must ensure the accountability in the specific area. Similarly, another important element belongs to these organizations is the participation of people in various matters. Although government bodies decide various matters and take decisions by the welfare of the society, however, the involvement of local people in decision making process is most important. The people living in a specific area have better knowledge about various problems

in the society, therefore, these people can address the problems more effectively and suggest various solutions. Therefore, successful governance practices of (Tripathy, Paliwal, & Nistala, 2021) local administrative organizations must be based on the participation of the people. Additionally, efficiency and value for the money is also the responsibility of government. To provide the resources to the general public and to maximize the resources and benefits from these resources for the general public is the major responsibility of the government. Therefore, local administrative organizations may help to resolve various issues related to the resources to the community. The government such as public administrative organizations should produce creative products and help the companies to produce creative products and increase the level of sustainability in natural resources. Therefore, local administrative organizations are based on the good governance practices which has influential role in the society.

2.2 Policies and Operational Strategies

Policies always play an influential role among the societies (Jenssen et al., 2019) and particularly when the policies are constructed by the government bodies has influential role to the development of the society. Similarly, the development of various local areas is based on the policies and strategic operations of government. The local areas generally face several problems and the solution of these problems may be handled with the help of policies and operational strategies of the local administrative organizations. It is the responsibility of these organizations to promote various policies and the development of policies is sufficient, however, the implementation of policies is important. In Thailand, there are number of local administrative organizations which are working particularly in Saraburi Province.

These organizations have developed a number of policies; however, the implementation of these policies is at lower level. It is important to implement all the policies developed by the public administrative organizations. The development as well as implementation of policies at lower level cannot provide the benefits to the society and it can decrease the level of governance by these organizations. Previous studies also highlighted that policy has central importance in administrative organizations (Nguyen Long & Krause, 2021). The success of these organizations is majorly based on the policies and operational strategies. Various operations working in different local areas of Thailand require valuable policies as well as strategies to work smoothly. It may help to increase the performance of these organizations. Therefore, development and implementation of successful policies and operational strategies has positive role to influence the success of these organizations. Therefore, it is hypothesized that;

H1: Policies and operational strategies has positive effect on success.

2.3 Leadership

Leadership is the ability of an individual or a group of individuals to influence and guide followers or other members of an organization (Tai, Chang, Hong, & Chen, 2012). It is one of the unique abilities among the individuals working in various organizations to guide the other employees and lead in various matters. Similar with other organizations, the leadership qualities among the local administrative organizations are also most important. Generally, the leadership belongs to the top management employees of the organizations. The top

management as well as the other management of the organization behave like a leader and they give the directions to their subordinates. The better ability of the leader to convince their employees towards a specific matter is most important and it must have the ability to resolve various problems. Leadership is also based on decision making power of a good leader which must have the important mental ability to take various decisions in difficult situation. Leadership always has positive role in the success of any organization (Van Zyl & Mathur-Helm, 2007). Similarly, the leadership is important in local administrative organizations working in Thailand. According to the literature, leadership has the ability to influence the activities of the business. This study proposed the leadership skills and the style of leadership among the managers in public administrative organizations which may have significant role to influence the level of success. Therefore, it is proposed that;

H2: Leadership has positive effect on success.

2.4 Public Participation

As the local government organizations are based on to implement various policies as well strategies in a specific area to resolve various problems and lead towards the development, therefore, the participation of general public in various matters is important. The problems faced by the general public in a specific place can be better explained by the general public. Therefore, while making policies as well as strategies, it is important to involve the public in different matters. The accuracy of decision making cannot be promoted without the participation of the public. It belongs to the communication between the general public and the government organizations in a specific area. The better communication between these two parties can lead to the solution of different problems in the society. As reported in previous studies that public participation is most important to resolve various problems in the society (Balla & Xie, 2020; Park, Butler, & Petrovsky, 2022). Therefore, the participation of public in various matters has the ability to influence the activities of the organization positively and the successful activities of these organizations lead to the success. To promote the level of success among these organizations, it is important to promote the participation of the people. Without the participation of the people in various problems and decision-making process, the activities of these organizations cannot be successful which may lead to the failure of different operations. Hence, this study proposed that public participation in Thailand with local government organizations lead to the success. Thus, it is proposed that;

H3: Public participation has positive effect on success.

2.5 Good governance principles

Governance is the way rules and norms as well as actions are structured, constant, regulated and held answerable. The degree of formality depends on the internal rules of a given organization and, externally, with its partners. The governance activity has central importance among the organizations because the governance is the most important part of success among organizations (Aasi, Rusu, Leidner, Perjons, & Corrales Estrada, 2018; Almaqtari, Farhan, Yahya, Al-Dalaien, & Shamim, 2022). The proper implementations of rules as well as norms is most important for smooth operations. And the smooth operations are the guarantee of

success among the organizations. Similarly, among the public administrative organizations, the importance of good governance cannot be neglected. The good governance is majorly based on the implementation of rules and regulations. It is also based on the transparency as well as accountability. Because the transparency and accountability among the public organizations lead towards the development of trust among the general public. Additionally, the effectiveness of ethics as well as morality can be achieved with the help of good governance of local administrative organizations. All these benefits of administrative organizations by applying good governance can have positive effect on the level of success. Different operations conducted by the organizations in different areas majorly based on the level of governance. Therefore, this study proposed that good governance principles are most important to implement. Therefore, the current study proposed the connection between governance and success of local administrative organizations. Thus, it is proposed that;

H4: Good governance principles has positive effect on success.

2.6 Human resources

Literature identified that the skills of the employees are the major instrument to get success. Among the organizations, the skills along with the capabilities of the employees lead the organization toward success (Muñoz-Pascual & Galende, 2020). Similarly human resources are most important which are based on the skills of the employees. A company having good human resources can achieve different objectives in less time and less cost. It is reported in the literature that human resources have significant effect on performance of the company's (Zehir, Karaboğa, & Başar, 2020). Therefore, to achieve higher performance it is important to have human resources and skillful workers as well as other capabilities. Similarly, according to the resource-based view the resources of any business has the ability to lead towards the higher performance (Dubey, Gunasekaran, Childe, Blome, & Papadopoulos, 2019). Resources in the current study is in the shape of human resources which are based on the skills and capabilities of the employees. Hence, this study highlighted the effect of human resources on success of local administrative organizations. The relationship between human resources and success is as follows;

H5: Human resources has positive effect on success.

2.7 Management Innovation

In the success of any organization, the innovation can always play most important role (Lestari, LEON, Widyastuti, BRABO, & Putra, 2020; Naveed, Alhaidan, Al Halbusi, & Al-Swidi, 2022). The application of innovation in various organizations lead towards efficiency. It helped the operations to complete before time. However, the management of innovation among these organizations is most important. Although there are several innovative ideas among the organizations, however, the implementation of valuable ideas is most important. The implementation of innovative ideas towards a valuable contribution is important. However, the extraction of valuable idea from the given information is not easy for the organizations. As innovation is depends upon the information gathered from different stakeholders, therefore, all the information cannot be valuable, therefore, the selection of valuable ideas and convert

towards the innovation is most influential part of local administrative organizations in Thailand. The low implementation of all the ideas of innovation cannot lead towards the success. Innovation is based on different types such as close innovation as well as open innovation (Hameed, Nisar, & Wu, 2021; Menne et al., 2022). Currently the models of the business organizations are moving towards the open innovation strategies. The open innovation strategies include the commercialization of ideas as well as products. In this way the management of innovation is most important which may have effect on the success of different operations. Therefore, it is proposed that;

H6: Management innovation has positive effect on success.

3. Methodology

The current study examined the relationship between policies and operational strategies, leadership, public participation, good governance principles, human resources, management innovation and success of local administrative organizations. This research employed a mixed research methodology combining quantitative and qualitative methods. For the quantitative research part, the research sample consisted of 400 residents in Saraburi Province. Saraburi is a province in central Thailand, northeast of Bangkok. The sample size was determined based on the criterion of 20 times the observed variables. They were selected via multi-stage sampling. Data were collected with the use of a questionnaire and analyzed with a structural equation modeling. As for the qualitative research component, in-depth interviews were conducted with 20 key informants consisting of executives of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province.

Questionnaire was developed by using the scale items from previous studies. Scale items was adapted from previous studies in which the minor changes were made. The reliability and validity of the scale items was examined due to the changes made in the scale items and by considering the contextual difference along with the different environment of the organizations. Therefore, pilot study is carried out by collecting 80 responses. Results of the pilot study confirmed all the scale items along with the reliability and validity. Hence, the complete scale was used to collect data from the respondents. Data statistics along with the normality of the data and significance value is reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Statistical test of empirical variables (n=400)

Variable	\bar{X}	S.D.	%CV	Sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
need	4.06	.99	24.38	-3.666	-3.866	28.386	.000
sunb	4.15	.94	22.65	-4.256	-3.932	33.575	.000
vion	3.79	1.09	28.76	-2.632	-4.555	27.671	.000
corg	4.13	.94	22.76	-4.178	-3.580	30.275	.000
know	3.67	1.08	29.43	-2.112	-3.849	19.276	.000
poly	3.84	1.04	27.08	-2.815	-4.104	24.768	.000
acti	4.10	.96	23.41	-4.115	-3.856	31.798	.000
effe	3.90	1.02	26.15	-2.881	-4.083	24.971	.000
resp	3.89	1.00	25.71	-2.744	-4.038	23.840	.000
trpa	3.60	1.10	30.56	-1.825	-3.720	17.167	.000
equa	3.71	1.15	31.00	-2.556	-4.933	30.871	.000
dece	3.89	1.05	26.99	-3.112	-4.376	28.829	.000
pepr	3.97	1.05	26.45	-3.672	-4.446	33.247	.000
svpr	3.96	1.06	26.77	-3.645	-4.363	32.320	.000
ogmn	3.95	1.03	26.08	-3.332	-4.127	28.133	.000
fnmn	4.02	.97	24.13	-3.430	-3.804	26.236	.000
quty	3.95	1.00	25.32	-3.229	-4.172	27.833	.000
prai	3.96	1.02	25.76	-3.373	-4.137	28.491	.000
coop	3.93	1.03	26.21	-3.197	-4.256	28.335	.000
conf	3.91	1.00	25.58	-2.959	-3.738	22.731	.000

4. Results

Results of the study are approached by using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) a most prominent data analysis technique in social sciences studies (Ali, Rasoolimanesh, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Ryu, 2018; Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015). Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is employed with the help of AMOS which is recommended software to analyze the data. The factor loadings are used to delete or retain the items. This study considered 0.7 as minimum level of factor loadings to retain the scale items. Results of factor loadings are reported in Table 2. It is found that all the scale items have factor loadings higher than 0.7. Therefore, none of the item is deleted from the current study. Furthermore, this study also examined discriminant validity (Hyland, Karatzias, Shevlin, & Cloitre, 2019) by using square root of AVE. Finally, the t-value and r-square value is also reported in Table 2 which has achieved the satisfactory level.

Table 2: Factor Loadings. (n = 400)

Variable	Factor Loading (λ)	Error (θ)	t	R ²
Policies and operational strategies (PYST)				
need	.92	.05	26.82	.95
Sunb $\rho_c = .78, \rho_v = .64$.62	.62	13.46	.38
Leadership (LEDR)				
vion	.74	.45	15.41	.55
corg	.76	.42	15.94	.58
Know $\rho_c = .82, \rho_v = .59$.81	.34	17.05	.6
Public participation (PARTI)				
poly	.98	.05	26.96	.95
Acti $\rho_c = .82, \rho_v = .70$.68	.54	15.23	.46
Good governance principles (GONAC)				
effe	.88	.23	21.38	.77
resp	.86	.26	20.96	.74
trpa	.83	.31	20.09	.69
equa	.84	.30	20.17	.70
Dece $\rho_c = .93, \rho_v = .73$.87	.24	21.67	.76
Human resources (HUOG)				
pepr	.98	.04	26.98	.96
Svpr $\rho_c = .93, \rho_v = .86$.88	.22	22.33	.78
Management innovation (INADM)				
ogmn	.98	.05	26.94	.95
Fnmn $\rho_c = .91, \rho_v = .84$.85	.27	21.12	.73
Success (SBLAO)				
quty	.93	.14	24.31	.86
prai	.96	.08	25.86	.92
coop	.92	.15	24.12	.85
Conf $\rho_c = .96, \rho_v = .84$.87	.25	21.72	.75

Note: Policies and operational strategies=PYST; Leadership=LEDR; Public participation=PARTI; Good governance principles=GONAC; Human resources=HUOG; Management innovation=INADM; Success=SBLAO

Structural model results are reported in Table 3 and the model of the study with results is reported in Figure 1. Structural model is employed by using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) (Hair et al., 2021; Hair Jr et al., 2021; Purwanto & Sudargini, 2021; Sarstedt, Hair Jr, Nitzl, Ringle, & Howard, 2020). Results of the study highlighted that; policies and operational strategies has positive effect on success of local administrative organizations. Leadership has positive effect on success of local administrative organizations. Furthermore, public

participation has positive effect on success of local administrative organizations. Additionally, good governance principles have positive effect on success of local administrative organizations. Human resources have positive effect on success of local administrative organizations. Finally, management innovation has positive effect on success of local administrative organizations

Table 3: Parameter estimation result of direct effect coefficient, indirect effect, and total effect from adjusting model (n=400)

Variable	Effect	Variable
		SBLAO R ² = .91
PYST	DE	.42*(8.24)
	IE	-
	TE	.42*(8.24)
LEDR	DE	.44*(7.34)
	IE	-
	TE	.44*(7.34)
PARTI	DE	.59*(6.89)
	IE	-
	TE	.59*(6.89)
GONAC	DE	.40*(9.03)
	IE	-
	TE	.40*(9.03)
HUOG	DE	.35*(4.84)
	IE	-
	TE	.35*(4.84)
INADM	DE	.59*(3.90)
	IE	-
	TE	.59*(3.90)
$\chi^2 = 243.96$ df = 131 p-value = .00000 , $\chi^2 / df = 1.86$, RMSEA = .046, RMR = .022, SRMR = .021, CFI = 1.00, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 266.43		

Note: Policies and operational strategies=PYST; Leadership=LEDR; Public participation=PARTI; Good governance principles=GONAC; Human resources=HUOG; Management innovation=INADM; Success=SBLAO

Figure 1: Model (n=400)

Note: Policies and operational strategies=PYST; Leadership=LEDR; Public participation=PARTI; Good governance principles=GONAC; Human resources=HUOG; Management innovation=INADM; Success=SBLAO

5. Conclusion

Results of the study reported that; policies and operational strategies, leadership, public participation, good governance principles, human resources and management innovation has positive relationship with the success of local administrative organizations. Improvement in these elements can improve the success of local administrative organizations. The management of problems such as leadership, policies, strategy management, human capability development and innovation has positive role to enhance good governance among these organizations which lead to the increase in rate of success among various operations. More specifically, the conclusion of the study is based on following three outcomes; 1) public participation, good governance principles, leadership, human resources in the organization, policies and operational strategies, management innovation, and success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi province were rated at a high level; 2) public participation, good governance principles, leadership, human resources in the organization, policies and operational strategies, and management innovation had an influence on the success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province, and 3) the model for the success in the management of local administrative organizations in Saraburi Province, developed by the researcher is called the 2PILGHS Model, consisting of P (referring to public participation), I (referring to management innovation), L (referring to leadership), P (referring to policies and operational strategies), G (referring to good governance), H (referring to human resources in the organization), and S (referring to success of local administrative organizations

in Saraburi Province). The 2PILGHS Model is a model for managing local government organizations through the use of concepts and creative, modern and timely methods aiming to serve people in the area and improve their quality of life.

6. Implications

The contribution of the study to the body of knowledge provided number of implications for the academicians. Number of problems covered by the current study in relation to the public administrative organizations was not addressed by the previous studies. The problem addressed by the study started a new debate in the field of public administrative organization success and it extended the literature. This study provided various unrevealed facts related to these organizations and provided the several recommendations. Study identified different factors which has influence on the success of these organization such as leadership, public participation, policies, strategic operations as well as various other factors which were not covered by the other studies in Saraburi Province. In this way, this study provided recommendations to the practitioners as well as management to improve the success rate among the operations of local administrative organizations. According to this study, the management of these organization should change the leadership style and effective leadership style should be adopted to promote the success rate. Additionally, it is recommended that maximum public participation should be involved in various decision-making process as well as planning activities of these organizations. Management of innovation must be improved by these organizations to enhance as well as to implement new ideas. Finally, these findings can be applied as a guideline for formulating policies that create sustainable success in the management of local administrative organizations.

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